

ANALYSIS OF THE LINGUISTIC FEATURES OF ECONOMIC DISCOURSE

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Abstract: This article provides a systematic analysis of the lexical and grammatical devices that shape the individuality of Uzbek journalistic-economic discourse. The study examines economic terminology, metaphorical expressions, evaluative vocabulary, and grammatical structures that contribute to the author’s stylistic identity. Based on the communicative-pragmatic features of the journalistic genre, the research identifies the stylistic characteristics of economic discourse and explains their functional roles within the discursive framework.

Keywords: journalistic discourse, economic discourse, lexical devices, grammatical devices, individuality, functional stylistics

For the analysis of Uzbek journalistic-economic discourse, widely read articles from the “Economy” section of the news portal *kun.uz* were selected as the primary object of study. The discursive examination of these texts begins with the specificity of their lexical devices.

The article titled “*The Moscow Exchange Has Come Under Sanctions. How Will This Affect the Ruble Exchange Rate?*” was chosen for analysis due to its economic-political orientation and its focus on the central issue of the stock exchange. Economic terminology within this article constitutes a considerable proportion of the entire text. These terms can be grouped into simple and complex terms (see Table1).

Simple Terms	Complex Terms
Simple lexical units	Simple nominal compounds
Sanction	• transactional costs
Exchange	• Ministry of Finance
Dollar	• currency market
Euro	• dollar trading
Trade	• financial institution
Ruble	• exchange-rate stabilization
Conversion	• online banking services
intermediary	• average value
Investor	• ruble volatility
Exporter	• secondary sanctions
Product	• money transfers
cost price	• currency shortage
Price	• banking reports
Revenue	• export revenues
	• Uzbekistan’s exports
	• primary market

Table 1. Classification of “currency”-related terminology by structural type

Among simple terms, both native Uzbek items (*mahsulot, tannarx, narx, tushum, savdo, vositachilik, eksportchi*) and borrowed terms (*sanction, exchange, dollar, euro, conversion, investor*) are observed.

Simple nominal terms typically appear in the *modifier + head* pattern (e.g., *currency market, dollar trading, financial institution, stabilization of the exchange rate*). In several cases, possessive or relational meaning emerges, as in *stabilization of the rate* or *currency shortage*. Many such structures express specialization or sector-specific meaning: *currency market, dollar trading, financial institution, money transfers*.

Compound terminological units also include tightly bound structures such as *online banks, average value, secondary sanctions, primary market*.

Multi-word compound terms generally consist of three-word sequences realized through either agreement-based or adjacency-based patterns: *currency-exchange points, unified market rate* (agreement). Governed structures also occur, such as *the rate for selling and buying currency*. The examples demonstrate that complex terms are formed through the template: [adjacency] + [agreement].

Another text titled “*How Does the Tax Committee Intend to Determine the Market Price of Goods?*” belongs to the same subtype of economic discourse. While the previous article focused on currency-related issues and terminology used in the currency market, the present text is centered around the concept of *taxation*.

Table 2. Terminology in the Real Estate Sales Discourse

Simple Terms	Complex Terms (Simple Compound)	Complex Terms (Multi-word Compound)
Activity	total trade	real estate market
Operation	trade volume	sale-purchase transactions
	rental fee	housing rental market
		secondary housing market
		average housing price increase
		secondary housing segment

This text focuses on the real estate sales discourse and shows how terminology reflecting individuality differs from previous tax discourse.

Table 3. Terminology in the Cooperative Law Discourse

Simple Terms	Complex Terms (Simple Compound)	Complex Terms (Multi-word Compound)
Farmer	supervision	agricultural cooperative
management	external audit	establishment of agricultural cooperatives
termination	reorganization	admission to cooperative membership
Norm	property relations	small producers
financing	coordination of activities	freedom of entrepreneurial activity
Cluster	farmer households	subjects of entrepreneurial activity
agribusiness		

This text concerns the discourse on cooperative law, highlighting economic and legal terminology and its individual characteristics. The terms differ from the previous real estate and tax discourse texts.

From the analysis of the tables presented above, the following generalizations can be made regarding the characteristics of lexical means that ensure the individual specificity of texts in economic discourse:

1. Existence of a Terminological System: Texts related to journalistic-economic discourse contain a system of terms specific to the respective field.
2. Structural Classification of Terms: Terms in journalistic-economic discourse can be classified into simple and compound structures.
3. Predominance of Compound Terms: A large portion of terms in this discourse appears as compounds, which in Uzbek are formed according to language-specific compounding methods and should be considered as linguistic units.
4. Representation in Lexicons: Compound terms are typically listed and explained in specialized domain dictionaries in their compound form.
5. Native and Borrowed Layers: Simple terms include both native and borrowed elements, and some general-purpose words acquire specialized meanings in the economic context.
6. Part-of-Speech Features: Simple terms are primarily nouns, but some also appear in verbal forms denoting actions.
7. Accessibility for the General Public: Most terms in journalistic-economic discourse are easily understandable to the general audience and, due to frequent usage in daily life, do not require additional explanations.

Grammatical Features of Uzbek Journalistic-Economic Discourse

In journalistic-economic discourse, daily economic reforms are analyzed, which requires the use of past, present, and future tense forms in texts. In the appendices, different tense forms are visually distinguished by color:

- Past tense – yellow
- Present tense – green
- Future tense – pink

This is because events that have occurred are analyzed, current situations are evaluated, and forecasts for future developments are provided. Therefore, the content of sentences cannot be strictly limited to a single tense.

This section analyzes the lexical and grammatical features of Uzbek journalistic-economic discourse texts. The study revealed that:

- Texts in the journalistic-economic discourse contain a systematic set of domain-specific terms, which can be classified into simple and compound terms.
- A significant portion of the terminology appears in the form of compound units, which should be considered as linguistic units in Uzbek.
- Among simple terms, both native and borrowed elements exist, and some general-purpose words acquire specialized meanings in the economic context.
- From a grammatical perspective, past, present, and future tense forms are used interchangeably, reflecting the analysis of past events, assessment of current situations, and forecasting of future developments.

In conclusion, investigating the lexical and grammatical features of Uzbek journalistic-economic discourse allows scholars to identify its terminological structure, individual style, and domain-specific linguistic characteristics.

References

1. Leontiev, A.N., Shakhovskiy, V.I., Bazhenova, I.S., et al. *Emotive Lexicon and Phraseology of the Russian Literary Language*. Moscow, 2008.

2. Volostnykh, I.A., Dimitrova, E.V., Zaykina, S.V., Voronin, L.V., Yashkina, E.A. *Psycholinguistics and Cognitive Semantics*. Saint Petersburg, 2010.
3. Bakirova, D.M. *Journalistic Discourse in Economics*. Tashkent, 2015.
4. Karimov, A. *Economic Terminology and Phraseology in the Uzbek Language*. Tashkent, 2017.
5. Crystal, D. *A Dictionary of Linguistics and Phonetics*. Oxford: Blackwell, 2010.
6. Lakoff, G., Johnson, M. *Metaphors We Live By*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 1980.
7. Rahmonov, S. *Lexical and Grammatical Means in the Journalistic-Economic Discourse*. Andijan, 2020.